

CAREER PREDICTION USING MACHINE LEARNING

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Abstract — Students should analyse their talents and identify their interests as they continue their education and follow the courses that interest them so that they may determine which job field their interests and abilities will place them in. This will assist them improve their performance and motivate their interests, allowing them to focus on and settle into their desired vocation. Also, after analysing prospects in all aspects, recruiters can use career recommender systems to determine which position the candidate should be retained in based on their performance and other evaluations. This essay is mostly concerned with forecasting the career field of IT applicants..

Keywords—decision tree, c5.0 algorithm

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's world, competition is becoming increasingly fierce. Students must be planned and organised from the beginning of their education in order to compete and reach the goal. It's critical to review their performance, discover their interests, and determine how near they are to their goal, as well as whether they're on the right track to reach their goal. It assists individuals in improving themselves, encouraging themselves to choose a better job path if their abilities aren't up to the task of accomplishing their objective, and pre-evaluating before entering the workforce.

Not only do recruiters analyse candidates on several aspects before making a final decision on whether to hire them or not, but they also locate a role and career area that best matches them if they are hired. Database administrator, business process analyst, developer, tester, data scientist, and other professions are just a few examples. To be placed in any of these roles, you must have prior knowledge. Recruiters use these abilities, talents, and interests to place candidates in roles that are a good fit for them. These types of prediction systems make it easier for them to recruit because, just like the entries, the recommendation is based on the entries.

II. LITERATURE ANALYSIS

Sharabiani et al. [1] provides valuable information to educational institution authorities. This information offers many opportunities for teachers and decision makers to improve the quality of their services and therefore help students to succeed in their training.

Elgamel et al [2] shows how to use educational data mining to predict student achievement in programming classes. Educators can benefit from identifying indicators that predict student programming performance.

Ramaswami et al [3] predicting the student's academic performance at a high level requires a large amount of academic, socio-economic and another environment. In addition, the selection of an appropriate algorithm for building the model uses Bayesian networks to predict the academic performance, economic attributes and other academic attributes.

Tulasi et al [4] Higher education has access to areas of data that can be used to improve decision-making. The use of big data and analytics in higher education is a relatively new area. The relevance of analytics is deeply felt in many fields and higher education is no different. This article examines the role of big data and analytics in higher education.

De Mauro et al [5] This study aims to clarify the heterogeneity of skills required in Big Data professions, by analyzing a large number of real job offers published online.

III. MOTIVATION

As students finish their studies and pursue the courses that interest them, it is critical that they analyse their talents and define their interests in order to choose which job field their interests and abilities will place them in. This will assist them improve their performance and motivate their interests, allowing them to focus on and settle into their desired vocation. Also, after examining candidates from all angles, recruiters can use this type of career recommender system to determine which position the candidate should be kept in based on their performance and other assessments. This essay primarily focuses on forecasting the career field of computer science applicants.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this paper is to find a Machine Learning model to predict the student career with the givendataset with accuracy. The model should be able to predict student job role. The dataset is divided into two training and testing data sets. The model should be trained with more data to get accuracy in learning. The c5.0 algorithm is the algorithm implemented in this paper.

The steps that require to be followed are:

1. Data Collection
2. Data Pre-processing
3. Model Building
4. Analyzing
5. Result

A. Data Collection: User have a dataset of students qualification details, the attributes of this dataset is used to train the model. There 20001 rows and 39 columns in dataset. The columns are headings and label. The heading denotes the qualifications of students. This dataset is used to predict the appropriate jobs for them.

B. Machine Learning: This is used to predict the student career. The machine learning algorithms are used to predict the value, from the given dataset. There are different classifiers present to predict the job role. The classifier accuracy relies on how it is trained. A classifier should need high accuracy.

1. Decision tree

Decision trees are a prominent machine learning classification problem that is also one of the simplest and easiest to construct. Many advanced algorithms, such as bagging, gradient boosting, and random forest, are based on decision trees. The XG Boost method is a more advanced variant of the general decision tree mentioned above. CART, C4.5, C5, and ID3 are some of the most often utilised decision trees. If the variable is digital, a node signifies an input variable (X) and a division over that variable. The leaf, also known as the terminal tree node, has an output variable (y) that is important for prediction.

A decision tree's normal procedure begins with the selection of a root node. Before the split, calculate the information gain or entropy for each of the nodes. Choose the node with the highest information gain or lowest entropy. Continue to split the knot and repeat the process. The process is repeated until no further splits are possible or the entropy is small. The metric for assessing uncertainty or randomness in data is entropy. The information gain metric estimates how much entropy is lowered before and after splitting.

$$H(S) = \sum_{x \in X} -p(x) \log_2 p(x)$$

$$IG(A, S) = H(S) - \sum_{t \in T} p(t)H(t)$$

V. BUILD MODEL

The model building is the main step. While building the model user use the algorithms. The steps involved are:

1. Import the packages that are necessary.

```
[1] import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
from sklearn import decomposition
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

from sklearn.preprocessing import LabelEncoder, OneHotEncoder

from sklearn.preprocessing import Normalizer

from sklearn import tree
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn import preprocessing
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
```

```
from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix, accuracy_score
```

Fig.1. Importing Package

2. Importing csv file

```
from google.colab import files
uploaded = files.upload()

roo_data.csv
• roo_data.csv(text/csv) - 4872181 bytes, last modified: 5/10/2018 - 100% done
Saving roo_data.csv to roo_data.csv

dataset = pd.read_csv("roo_data.csv")
```

Fig.2. Importing Dataset

3. Conversion of data into normalized form

```
[12] data1=data[:,14]

[13] normalized_data = Normalizer().fit_transform(data1)
print(normalized_data.shape)

(20000, 14)

[14] normalized_data

array([[0.28508989, 0.26029947, 0.32227553, ..., 0.01652695,
0.0330539 ],
[0.34997994, 0.27818918, 0.32754533, ..., 0.00448692, 0.00897384,
0.01346077],
[0.29581244, 0.35733901, 0.37811453, ..., 0.01662042, 0.0041551 ,
0.01246531],
...,
[0.3430836 , 0.28934762, 0.33068299, ..., 0.02480122, 0.00826707,
0.01240061],
[0.29479286, 0.37716094, 0.39450167, ..., 0.01734073, 0.03901665,
0.02167592],
[0.31140896, 0.32847247, 0.31567484, ..., 0.00426588, 0.02986113,
0.02559526]])
```

Fig.2. Data Normalization

4. Suggested job role.

```
[20] y=pd.DataFrame(label,columns=["Suggested Job Role"])
y.head()

Suggested Job Role
0 7
1 18
2 18
3 28
4 2
```

Fig.3. Job Suggestion

5. Perform Decision tree classifier.

```
[22] X_train,X_test,y_train,y_test=train_test_split(X1,y,test_size=0.2,random_state=10)

[23] clf = tree.DecisionTreeClassifier()
clf = clf.fit(X_train, y_train)

[24] from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix, accuracy_score

[25] y_pred = clf.predict(X_test)

[26] y_pred

array([20, 6, 15, ..., 14, 28, 28])
```

Fig.4. Decision Tree Classifier

6. Then identify on test set and calculate the accuracy of model.

```
[27] cm = confusion_matrix(y_test,y_pred)
      accuracy = accuracy_score(y_test,y_pred)

[28] print("confusion matrix=",cm)
      print(" ")
      print("accuracy=",accuracy*100)

confusion matrix= [[3 7 2 ... 2 2 1]
 [1 2 1 ... 4 2 3]
 [3 1 3 ... 2 1 4]
 ...
 [2 2 2 ... 6 0 5]
 [4 5 3 ... 3 4 8]
 [4 2 1 ... 4 2 2]]

accuracy= 2.9250000000000003
```

Fig.4. Accurate Rate

The accuracy is 2.925%.

VI. RESULT

Using the provided training and test datasets, the result indicates the anticipated career of student 2.925. The background algorithm is c5.0, and fresh predictions are continually added to the dataset to improve accuracy.

```
accuracy= 2.9250000000000003
```

VII. CONCLUSION

Student career prediction is one of the important research areas in this current digital field world. Traditionally, various survey methods are used to predict student career. But these methods take a long time to predict the outcome. In this model, we use a dataset containing academic information about students through which we can predict suitable jobs for them, which takes less time and is more accurate than traditional methods. In this research paper to predict student career using decision tree and c5.0 approach. From the concepts mentioned above, the model produces a better result in terms of accuracy value.

VIII. REFERENCES

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